

CHEMISTRY

ISOMERIZATION OF N-BUTANE WITH THE PARTICIPATION OF CATALYSTS OF SULFATED ZIRCONIUM DIOXIDE

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Abstract

In the presented article, catalytic systems consisting of metal-modified HMOR, HZSM-5 zeolites and sulfated zirconium dioxide, capable of isomerizing n-Butane with high isoselectivity at normal atmospheric pressure and low temperature, were synthesized. The role of each component of the catalytic systems in the process was clarified, it was shown that the ZrO₂ component of the system lowers the process temperature, cobalt ensures the stability of the catalytic system, and sulfate anions cause high isomerizability. The optimal temperature of the process is determined to be 180-190°C. N-butane conversion is 48% on the 0.4%Co/HMOR/10%ZrO₂ - SO₄²⁻ (2%) catalytic system at 190°C, MHS=2 hour⁻¹, H₂:CH = 3:1, QSH2 = 350 hour⁻¹, isoselectivity was 70%. It was known that the conversion of n-butane on the synthesized catalytic system takes place by a bimolecular mechanism.

Keywords: isomerization, n-butane, sulfated zirconium dioxide, zeolite, isoselectivity, low temperature, conversion.

Introduction

Isomerization of alkanes is carried out in industry to obtain isoalkanes of low molecular weight (isobutane, isopentane, isomeric hexanes), as well as weakly branched higher alkanes with low freezing points. Low molecular weight isoalkanes are added to motor gasolines to increase the octane number of the head fractions boiling up to 70 °C. Isobutane and isopentane are also used as starting products for the production of unsaturated hydrocarbons - isobutylene and isoprene; in addition, isobutane is also a raw material for alkylation processes.

Thermodynamically, low temperature enables deeper isomerization with the formation of highly branched isoalkanes, therefore, low-temperature isomerization processes in the presence of highly active catalysts are of great importance.

One of the low-temperature solid superacid catalysts of n-alkanes is sulfated zirconium dioxide catalysts. SO₄²⁻/ZrO₂ based catalysts are characterized by high activity, resistance to poisons and favorable temperature range (140-220°C). Butane isomerization in the presence of such catalysts is widely studied. [1] reports on persulfate-modified ZrO₂ solid superacids and their activity in n-butane isomerization. Factors affecting their properties, including the annealing temperature, persulfate absorption density, and ZrO₂ source preparation conditions, are studied. It is shown that the sample prepared with 0.25-0.50 mol/l persulfate impregnation and then annealing at 600-650°C has the highest degree of acidity. Compared to sulfated zirconium dioxide prepared under the same conditions, persulfated zirconium dioxide at 250°C shows a twice as high activity in the isomerization of n-butane, which is explained by the fact that it has more medium-strength acid centers.

The strength of the acid centers of the catalyst is also affected by its promotion with other metal oxides.

It was shown in [2] that the promotion of sulfated zirconium dioxide with alumina (ASZ) improves its catalytic activity in the isomerization of n-butane. The activity and stability of sulfated zirconium dioxide catalysts are investigated in three different nanostructures: ASZ supported on MCM-41, ASZ nanoparticles, and Al₂O₃-promoted mesoporous sulfated zirconium dioxide. The increase in activity was primarily determined by the amount of Al₂O₃ addition and the annealing temperature. The high activity and stability of Al₂O₃-promoted catalysts is due to the improved distribution of the strength of acid centers. The amount of Al₂O₃ in all three catalysts can be adjusted to obtain optimal catalytic activity in butane isomerization. Butane conversion is 6 times higher than in unpromoted SZ catalysts. This is due to the abundance of weak Brønsted acid centers of moderate strength on optimal catalysts. The activity is most stable for the nanoparticulate form of sulfated zirconium dioxide, which is due to the optimal distribution of weak Brønsted acid centers. On the other hand, very strong Brønsted acid centers cause a rapid decrease in activity due to coking and cracking. It was concluded that, firstly, mesoporous carriers can promote better dispersion of sulfated tetragonal ZrO₂; second, the addition of Al₂O₃ can prevent the conversion of tetragonal sulfated zirconium dioxide to monoclinic sulfated zirconium dioxide; thirdly, the high activity and stability of Al₂O₃-promoted catalysts is due to the optimized distribution of the strength of acid centers. The maximum catalytic activity for the three studied catalysts - ASZ-MCM-41, ASZ-NP and AS/MPZrO₂ - is associated with the corresponding optimal distribution of acid centers. The addition of Al₂O₃ results in an increase in weak Brønsted acid centers with intermediate force that is important for maintaining a stable catalytic cycle in butane isomerization. A general reaction mechanism of isomerization of n-butane over sulfated zirconium dioxide is proposed and two conclusions are

reached: firstly, the bimolecular mechanism is the main direction in the initial period on strong Brensted acid centers. The initial decrease in activity occurs as a result of coking at strong Brensted acid sites and clogging of mesoporous channels. Second, the weak Brensted acid centers play an important role in maintaining the stable transformation in the later period. In addition, the high activity of the nanoparticle catalyst (ASZ-NP) with slight fragmentation suggests that its more open pore system can better prevent mesopore clogging. As can be seen from here, the porosity of the selected carrier has an important effect on the activity of the catalyst. It is shown in [3] that the effect of hydrogen on the isomerization of n-butane on Pt/SO₄²⁻-ZrO₂ and hybrid Pt/SiO₂+SO₄²⁻-ZrO₂ (a physical mixture of Pt/SiO₂ and SO₄²⁻-ZrO₂) catalysts depends on the reaction conditions (temperature, partial pressure of hydrogen) depends. At high reaction temperature under low hydrogen pressure, the reaction composition due to hydrogen is close to zero, and at low reaction temperature under higher hydrogen pressure, it is negative (-0.5-1.0). The negative effect of hydrogen on activity is believed to be due to the hydride formed by the phenomenon of hydrogen diffusion. It was determined that C₄ olefins and C₈ hydrocarbons are not reaction intermediates, and the reaction mechanism of n-butane isomerization is a monomolecular mechanism. The reaction parameters are similar in Pt/SO₄²⁻-ZrO₂ and Pt/SiO₂+SO₄²⁻-ZrO₂ catalysts. This indicates that the hydrogen effect is universal on the catalyst surface, and the proximity of Pt and acid centers is not so important. In [4], a palladium-containing catalyst based on unbound granular sulfated zirconium dioxide was studied for the isomerization of n-butane. It was determined that the isomerization of the n-butane fraction under optimal conditions at 140-150°C allows obtaining a high yield of isobutane (up to 52% by mass). [5] investigated the effect of hydrogen on the catalytic activity of Fe- and Mn-promoted sulfated zirconium dioxide catalysts. It was determined that the effect of hydrogen on the activity of Fe-promoted SZ in the isomerization of n-butane depends significantly on the amount of Fe in the catalyst. It was also found that the negative effect of hydrogen is

greater at lower temperatures. It is assumed that the reason for the decrease in activity in the presence of hydrogen is its interaction with reaction intermediates.

Purpose of the research

The aim of the present work is to study the isomerization of butane at low temperature and normal atmospheric pressure over a catalyst based on sulfated zirconium dioxide (SZ) and metal-modified zeolites.

Experimental part

The object of the study is catalytic systems consisting of cobalt-modified HMOR₁₇, HZSM-5 zeolites and sulfated zirconium dioxide. These catalysts were prepared by sol-gel method [6]. Cobalt-modified zeolite components of the synthesized catalytic systems were obtained by keeping decationized zeolite (HMOR17 and HZSM-5) in cobalt nitrate solution of a certain concentration for 24 hours, then evaporation of the aqueous phase, drying at 120°C and 350°C (3 hours) and 550°C (5 hours) and at 380°C prepared by processing in hydrogen flow (40 ml/min; 3 h).

When synthesizing the SZ component of catalytic systems, zirconium dioxide gel was first obtained. For this, a certain amount of ZrOCl₂ taken was hydrolyzed with 25% ammonia solution at pH = 8-9 [6]. For this purpose, ammonia solution was added dropwise with stirring to the solution obtained by dissolving 10 g of ZrOCl₂·8H₂O in 300 ml of H₂O heated to 80°C. The obtained gel was kept in the solution at 80°C for 2 hours, then it was filtered, washed with distilled water and dried at 100°C (24 hours). Then, the resulting Zr(OH)₄ gel was sulfated with (NH₄)₂SO₄ solution (with stirring for 2 hours) and the aqueous fraction was evaporated to wet state. According to EACP (ICP - MS) data, the amount of sulfur in the synthesized SZ was 1.97 wt.%.

To complete the synthesis of the catalytic systems, the obtained SZ was thoroughly mixed with the cobalt-modified zeolite component powder until visually homogeneous. The obtained mass was dried at 120°C (3 hours), annealed at 600°C and 550°C (5 hours), then powdered and mixed with a binder - Al₂O₃ hydrogel, made into 1.5 × 3 ÷ 4 mm grains, and the thermal treatment described above was carried out again. The composition of the synthesized catalytic systems is shown in table 1.

Table 1.

Composition of synthesized catalysts

Catalyst	Composition
Sign	
M-1	0.4%Co/HMOR
M-2	0.4%Co/HMOR/10%ZrO ₂
M-3	HMOR/10%ZrO ₂ - SO ₄ ²⁻ (2%)
M-4	0.4%Co/HMOR/10%ZrO ₂ - SO ₄ ²⁻ (2%)
K-2	0.4%Co/HZSM-5/10%ZrO ₂ - SO ₄ ²⁻ (2%)

As a raw material, liquefied n-butane, TU51-946-80, n-butane-96.5% by mass, produced by VNIPIGas Experimental Plant (Orenburg, RF) was used.

The isomerization of n-butane was studied in a flow-type catalytic laboratory setup equipped with a quartz reactor. The volume of the catalyst loaded into the reactor was changed between 1-5 cm³. Before the

experiment, the catalysts were reduced with hydrogen at 380°C (2 hours).

The reaction products were analyzed using an Au-toSystemXL chromatograph.

Results and Discussion

In order to study the isomerizing activity of the synthesized catalysts in n-butane conversion, the role of the components included in the catalysts (zeolite,

metal added to zeolite, ZrO_2 and finally SO_4^{2-} anions) in this process was studied sequentially.

Preliminary studies of decationized forms of ZSM-5 (modulus 23) zeolite and synthetic mordenite (modulus 17) have shown that ZSM-5 zeolites are almost inactive in the conversion of n-butane, while HMOR is active at 250-350°C. During the conversion,

isobutane, propane, n- and isopentane are formed. By the 20th minute of the reaction, the yield of isobutane increases and reaches the maximum value (13.8% at 300°C), and then decreases to 3.9% at the 60th minute (Figure 1). The maximum yield of propane, a byproduct of the reaction, reaches 27% at the beginning of the reaction and then decreases to 12% within 60 minutes.

Figure 1. Time dependence of *i*-butane yield over HMOR catalyst
 $T=300^{\circ}C$, $QHS = 150 \text{ hour}^{-1}$.

Isopentane and pentane yields remain at 2.5-2.8 and 1.0-1.5%, respectively, over 60 minutes. When the temperature is reduced to 250°C, the yield of propane decreases more than the yield of isobutane, which leads to an increase in the selectivity in the direction of the isomerization reaction.

The inclusion of cobalt in the composition of mordenite (catalyst M-1) increases its activity and stability in the conversion of n-butane. The effect of cobalt on the activity of HMOR depends on the process temperature. When the temperature is increased to 300°C, the yield of isobutane in cobalt mordenite is 16.3%. The obtained results are presented in table 2.

Table 2.

Conversion of n-Butane over H-mordenite and its Co-modified form (M-1).
 $QHS = 150 \text{ hour}^{-1}$, $H_2 : n-C_4H_{10} = 2 : 1$.

Katalizator	T, °C	Composition of catalysts, wt. % *					
		C ₁ – C ₂	C ₃ H ₈	<i>i</i> -C ₄ H ₁₀	n-C ₄ H ₁₀	<i>i</i> -C ₅ H ₁₂	n-C ₅ H ₁₂
HMOR ₁₇	300	–	27.2	15.5	53.1	2.8	1.4
M-1	220	0.4	10.8	12.9	71.1	3.3	1.5
	300	0.5	34.8	16.3	44.8	2.6	1.0

*- 20th minute

The release of isobutane in HMOR reaches a maximum value at 20 minutes and then decreases. In M-1, the output of isobutane is more stable and decreases after the 40th minute of the reaction. This indicates that cobalt has a significant stabilizing effect on the activity of mordenite. As can be seen from Table 2, the main products of conversion of n-butane over HMOR and M-1 catalysts are propane, isobutane, isopentane, n-pentane and a small amount of C1-C2 hydrocarbons.

Modification of M-1 with zirconium dioxide (catalyst M-2) allows to increase the yield of isobutane and lower the reaction temperature. For example, in primary dealuminated mordenite at 220°C, the conversion of n-butane is 24.5%, and the yield of isobutane is 12.0%. The inclusion of 10% ZrO_2 in the composition of the catalyst sample allows to increase the conversion of butane by 2.2 times and the yield of isobutane by 2.4 times compared to HMOR (table 3).

Table 3.

Conversion of n-Butane over HM and cobalt-mordenite-zirconium catalyst (M-2).

Catalyst	T, °C	Conversion of n-butane, %	yield, wt. %	
			<i>i</i> -butane Изобу-тан	<i>i</i> -pentane
HMOR ₁₇	220	24.5	12.0	0.6
M-2	190	12.7	9.1	1.6
	220	54.5	28.5	5.3

The inclusion of sulfate anions in the composition of the catalyst significantly changes its activity. The effect of sulfation on the activity of mordenite catalysts is shown in table 4.

Table 4.

Conversion of n-butane over mordenite-zirconium-sulfate (M-3) and sulfated cobalt-mordenite-zirconium (M-4) catalysts.

Catalyst	T, °C	Conversion of n-C ₄ H ₁₀ , %	Yield, wt. %		
			C ₃ H ₈	i- C ₄ H ₁₀	i-C ₅ H ₁₂
M-3	190	36.4	7.5	25.7	2.6
	200	46.1	11.7	27.7	4.6
	220	50.3	14.5	30.0	4.9
M-4	190	47.6	16.4	33.5	4.7

According to the table, the conversion of n-butane is 36.4-50.3% and the yield of i-butane is between 25.7-30.0% in the temperature interval of 190-220°C on the given type of catalysts. A noticeable increase in the activity of catalysts after sulfation is observed at 190°C. The conversion of n-butane increases from 12.7% to 36.4%, and the yield of i-butane increases from 9.1% to 25.7% (tables 3 and 4). However, the yield of the main byproduct of the reaction - propane increases faster than the yield of isobutane as the temperature increases, which is accompanied by a decrease in the isoselectivity of the reaction.

Thus, the obtained results show that during the conversion of butane at a temperature of 190°C on a dealuminated mordenite-based M-4 catalyst with a silicate module of 17, the yield of i-butane is 33.5 mass %, and the conversion of n-butane is 47.6%, in this case, the selectivity for the target product is 70.4% does.

Table 3 also shows the results of the study of the activity of the cobalt-free HMOR/SZ (M-3) catalyst in the conversion of n-butane. A comparison of the activities of M-3 and M-4 catalysts, which differ in cobalt composition, shows that the inclusion of Co in the catalyst composition increases the conversion of n-butane by 11.2%, and the yield of i-butane by 7.8% (at 190°C). The difference between the activities of these catalysts can be explained by the occurrence of hydrogen spillover on the surface of the catalyst in the presence of Co. During this event the Co metal on the surface of the catalyst homolytically dissociates the H₂ molecules supplied to the system into H atoms [7].

Processed H atoms "flow" to the surface of the ZS component, turning into hydride ions (H⁻) and protons

in Lewis acid centers, increasing the amount of such centers by forming acid centers that do not differ from the acid centers present on the surface of the catalyst. The activity of the catalyst is related to these centers.

The comparative analysis of reaction products on different mordenite catalysts is important from the point of view of the mechanism of n-butane conversion process. With the modification of zeolite, not only the conversion of n-butane, but also the distribution of conversion products changes. At this time, the presence of C₅ hydrocarbons in the products is of particular importance. The formation of pentane and propane is the result of the bimolecular interaction of n-butane molecules, in other words, the process proceeds with the formation of an active bimolecular C₈+ intermediate [8, 9]. The decomposition of this component into i-butane, i-pentane and propane depends on the conditions of the reaction, the catalyst, taking into account the acidic nature of the activation of such reactions, and the acidity of the catalyst. Indeed, promotion of the M-2 catalyst with sulfuric acid, i.e. conversion of the catalyst into a superacid [9, 10] leads to the selective formation of i-C₄H₁₀ and a significant increase in the activity of the catalyst.

The observed regularities of the effect of the modification of HMOR zeolite on the conversion of n-butane are also manifested during the modification of HZSM-5 zeolite. Here, too, modification with Co, ZrO₂ and sulfate anion leads to an increase in the isomerizing activity and a decrease in the isomerization temperature. The activity of catalysts M-4 and K-6 in the conversion of n-butane can be compared based on the data of table 5.

Table 5.

Conversion of n-Butane over K-6 and M-4 catalysts. QHS = 150 hour⁻¹, H₂ : n-C₄H₁₀ = 2 : 1.

T, °C	K-6			M-4		
	Conversion, %	Selectivity, %		Conversion, %	Selectivity%	
		i - C ₄	C ₃ +C ₅		i-C ₄	C ₃ +C ₅
160	34.0	68.1	31.9	39	67.5	32.5
180	38	72	28	47.6	70	30
200	46.0	51.5	48.5	54	52.8	47.2

As can be seen from the table, the isomerizing activity of both catalysts first increases and then decreases as the temperature increases, and the isomerizing activity of these catalysts is close to each other. 180°C can be chosen as the optimal isomerization temperature.

Based on the results given in the table, it can be concluded that the formation of the bimolecular intermediate takes place with the participation of the SZ (SO₄²⁻ - ZrO₂) component of the compositional catalytic system.

Thus, the catalytic system developed on the basis of sulfated zirconium dioxide and metal-modified zeolites is capable of isomerizing butane with high isoselectivity (70%) and conversion at low temperature (180°C) and normal atmospheric pressure. Isomerization of n-butane on the synthesized catalytic system proceeds with the formation of bimolecular intermediates.

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